

Short Communication

Assessment of Gender and Age - Related Prevalence of Malaria in Birnin Kebbi,
Kebbi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Malaria remains one of the most complex and debilitating parasitic diseases in many regions of the world. A cross sectional study was carried out to assess gender and age - related prevalence of malaria in Birnin Kebbi using the rapid test kits (RTD). Blood samples were collected from consenting family members by cleaning the thumb with alcohol swab and pricking using a sterile lancet. Thereafter, the drop of blood collected is tested for malaria using rapid diagnostic test kit (RTD). Out of the 300 samples tested, 62(20.7%) were positive for malaria. The distribution between males and females were not significantly different (Males: 52.7% Vs Females: 47.3%; $P > 0.05$). Prevalence of infection, though highest among subjects of age group 11-20 years (31.4%) and lowest among younger children of 0-10 years (13.3%), showed no significant variation in distribution ($P=0.113$). It was therefore concluded that malaria was prevalent in Birnin Kebbi, and neither gender nor age of the residents is of significant influence on its distribution at Birnin Kebbi. Therefore, further studies on socioeconomic, environmental, behavioural or other malaria related factors are needed to ascertain the determinants of the disease in the community.

Keywords: Age, Assessment, Gender, Kebbi and Malaria,

Received: 12/11/21

Accepted: 14/05/22

Introduction

Malaria is caused by a protozoan parasite of the genus *Plasmodium*, and remains the most prevalent tropical disease in the world today. Each year, it causes disease in approximately 650 million people and kills between one to three million, most of them, young children in sub-Saharan Africa. It is one of the deadly widespread of all parasitic diseases in the world (Guinovart *et al.*, 2006; Vaughan *et al.*, 2008). The four known species of *Plasmodium* genus that cause human malaria are *Plasmodium falciparum*, *Plasmodium vivax*, *Plasmodium ovale* and *Plasmodium malariae* (Duchemin *et al.*, 2001) and they are a major human health problem in malaria endemic regions of the world (Mohan and Ramaswamy, 2007). Records have shown that at least 60 percent of the Nigerian population suffer from at least one episode of malaria each year and remains one of the world's greatest childhood killers and is significant impediment to social and economic development in the tropics (Okunye *et al.*, 2015). Majority of cases commonly reported are from children less than five years of age and from pregnant women (Greenwood *et al.*, 2005). Published data indicate that malaria causes mortality of about 25% of young children under five years old, 30% of childhood mortality and 11% of maternal mortality. Various reports have suggested that there's no scientific evidence to support that susceptibility to malaria infection is gender based (Abdullahi *et al.* 2009; Okonko *et al.*, 2012). Rather it is opined that infection is a function of the individual's exposure to mosquito bites in malaria endemic areas (Yohanna *et al.*, 2019). Against this backdrop, this study was conducted to determine the relationship between malaria infection and age/gender of residents in Birnin Kebbi.

Materials and Methods

Study area

Birnin Kebbi is the capital city of Kebbi State in Northwestern Nigeria. It is located approximately between latitudes 12° 27' 57.8808" N and longitudes 4° 11' 58.2864" E. It is also the Headquarters of the Gwandu emirate council. The State was created from the old Sokoto State on August 27th, 1991. It comprises of 21 local government areas and four emirate councils (Argungu, Gwandu, Yauri and Zuru). Kebbi State as a total land area of approximately 37,728 sq. km, with a population of 3,256,541 people (NPC, 2010). The dwellers in Birnin - Kebbi are mostly civil servants, traders and a few farmers.

Methods

A total of 300 individuals gave blood samples for analysis from six areas in Birnin Kebbi. Fifty (50) samples were collected from each of the sampling stations. Other relevant epidemiological information were obtained by administration of structured

questionnaires. Participants were then tested using the rapid diagnostic test kit for malaria. Blood was obtained from the subjects' left-hand thumb. First the thumb is disinfected by cleaning with an alcohol swab and then pricked with a sterile blood lancet. The finger is then squeezed until blood appeared, from which a drop is taken and placed in the round whole of the test kit to allow a 10 minutes reaction. The result is observed and read as recommended by World Health Organization (WHO, 2015).

Reading the Strip test result

If one line appears on the test window i.e. only the control line appears, the result is negative. If two lines appear (both the test and control line) on the test window it means that the test is positive. But if no line appears on the test window, it means that the result is invalid.

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained were entered into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences, Version 25.0 (SPSS Inc. Chicago, USA) for analysis. Results obtained were presented in simple descriptive statistics. Chi square test was used to compare differences in categorical variables. Values were considered significant at $P < 0.05$.

Results

Epidemiological characteristics of the study population

Epidemiological information of the study population is presented in Table 1. The majority (41.7%) of the population were adults in the age group 21-30 years, while only 15.0% of young children in the age group (0 – 10 years) participated. With respect to gender, the population consists of more males (52.7%) than females (47.3%). As it relates to education, most (74.0%) of the participants were literate, as compared to those with no formal education (26.0%) in the study. The majority (56.3%) of participants have no knowledge about the transmission of malaria.

Overall and gender Prevalence of Malaria among Study Population in Birnin - Kebbi

Overall, malaria was present in 40 out of 300 (20.7%) subjects examined. prevalence of malaria with respect to gender, showed a lower prevalence among males (19.6%) than females (21.8%). However, the distribution was not statistically significant ($P=0.631$) as presented in Table 2.

Age Prevalence of Malaria among Study Population in Birnin - Kebbi

Table 2 depicts distribution of malaria among age categories. There were more cases (31.4%) recorded among subjects of age group 11 – 20, followed by those in the age

group 21 – 30years (21.6%). Prevalence was lowest among the younger children of age 0-10years (13.3%). Overall, distribution with respect to age did not vary significantly (P = 0.113).

Table 1: Epidemiological characteristics of the study population

Factor	Category	Total number	Percentage (%)
Age	0-10	45	15.0
	11 -20	51	17.0
	21 – 30	125	41.7
	>30	79	26.3
Sex	Male	158	52.7
	Female	148	47.3
Education	Has Formal education	222	74.0
	No formal education	78	26.0
Knowledge about transmission	Yes	131	43.7
	No	169	56.3
Total		300	100

Table 2: Distribution of malaria stratified by sex and age of subjects in Birnin Kebbi

Demographic factor	Category	Prevalence	%	P-value
Overall		40/300	20.7	
Age	0 - 10	6/45	13.3	0.113
	11 - 20	16/51	31.4	
	21 - 30	27/125	21.6	
	>30	13/79	16.5	
Sex	Male	31/158	19.6	0.637
	Female	31/148	21.8	

Discussion

Demographic studies of malaria serve an important public health role since they are key to identifying relevant factors that could be manipulated to control it. The disease, though preventable and curable still remains a global concern in spite of the progress made through the years to curb its scourge especially among endemic populations. According to the World Health Organization, Nigeria and three other African countries (The Democratic Republic of Congo, United Republic of Tanzania and Mozambique) account for about half of all malaria deaths globally in 2020 (WHO, 2021).

The overall prevalence of malaria (20.7%) in this study is low compared to the data reported by Olasunkanmi *et al.*, 2013 (31.0%) in Abeokuta, Singh *et al.*, 2014 (59.6%) in Aliero, and Kunihya *et al.*, 2016 (51.9%) in Niger State, Nigeria. This observation might reflect the impact of the Government's control efforts against malaria in the State. The high prevalence of malaria among females (21.8%) in this study agrees with the findings of Nwaorgu and Orajaka (2011) who reported higher malarial burdens in females (54.9%) than their male counterparts (47.0%). Although it has been opined that females, due to their constant exposure during domestic chores, especially early mornings when mosquito bites are highest, are likely to bear more parasite loads than the males. Our work did not find any significant gender related effect on the distribution of malaria. This agrees with the observations of Bassey and Nwakuka (2017) who reported that gender did not confer any significant influence on the burden of infection among subjects. Here, it might therefore be suggested that susceptibility to malarial infection is not a function of gender, but could be a factor that depends on the individual's exposure to infectious bites of the mosquito vector. However, in some societies, complex gender associated differences due to socio-cultural values and expectations, exposure patterns may result in higher infection rates among women folks and children (Yohanna *et al.*, 2019).

Similarly, distribution of malaria infection in this study, found no age-related pattern ($P=0.113$). Young children within age group of 0-10 years were less infected (13.3%). This could be attributed to the preventive maternal care (such as sleeping under treated mosquito nets, use of repellants etc) they enjoy from parents. But the highest rate, however, was recorded in the immediate age group of 11-20 years (31.4%). It appears that children, the older they become the less they care to stay at home. They spend more time playing outdoors with mates, accompany parents to places of primary occupation such as farms, mosquito laden workshops, field works, and are therefore more exposed to several mosquito bites. This report agrees with the findings of other studies where higher burdens of malaria in older children have been reported (Abah *et al.*, 2016, Richard *et al.*, 2019). However, from age groups 21-30years and above 30years old, malaria infection

decreased with increase in age which may suggest that they had either received a form of treatment, have acquired partial immunity possibly due to several exposures or are able on their own to take preventive measures (Alessandro and Lorenzo, 2012).

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that malaria remains a significant public health problem in Birnin - Kebbi. Gender and age did not influence prevalence significantly. All subjects were equally exposed to malaria infection. Therefore, further studies on socioeconomic, environmental, behavioural or other malaria related factors are needed to ascertain the determinants of the disease in the community.

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